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An Arterial Parameter Estimation Technique using a 1D Frequency Domain Model

Author:
Kaizad K Wadia

College Identifier:
02089502

Supervisor:
Dr. Georgios Papadakis

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Abstract

In the present report a 1D frequency domain analytical model for wave propagation in networks of mammalian arteries is expanded and used to estimate arterial parameters for five test cases. These test cases include the upper thoracic aorta, common carotid artery, tapered aorta, single bifurcation and full aorta. For each of these test cases a set of input parameters are defined that must be determined using time variant values of pressure and volume flow rate that are obtained from a previously conducted 3D numerical simulation. The input parameters of this simulation are known, and are attempted to be redetermined using this estimation procedure. The estimation of these parameters yields a relative deviation of typically less than 20%. This estimation procedure is furthermore verified by performing it on data obtained from the same 1D model with the known values of the inputs and as such must rediscover the same values of the parameters. In this case the estimation technique is able find the exact values of these parameters.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

In cardiovascular research, determining arterial properties are of utmost importance due to them being key determinants in the development of cardiovascular diseases. This is especially the case in atherosclerosis, which is the thickening and hardening of the arteries due to a buildup of plaque in the arterial lining. However, many properties such as thickness and stiffness are not easy to measure noninvasively. That being said, blood flow properties such as blood pressure and volume flow rate may be measured noninvasively. They may also be computed using hemodynamic models, which are useful tools that are capable of simulating blood flows in arteries.

However, many simulations such as computational fluid dynamics ones are computationally expensive, making them highly impractical to use for the purposes of parameter estimation. This is because parameter estimation techniques typically require the simulation to be run many times. That is why 1 dimensional models, (which determine pressure and flow rate along one spatial dimension) are useful as they are less computationally intensive as 3D models. This is especially true for the model currently used, which is an analytical model in the frequency domain that is significantly faster than many currently available models.

The purpose of this project is to use a 1D analytical model in the frequency domain and the results of a 3D numerical simulation using known input parameters to estimate the same parameters for a few test cases of arterial networks. These test cases include the upper thoracic aorta, common carotid artery, tapered aorta, single bifurcation and full aorta. To realise this, a 1D analytical model previously developed is implemented in code and a parameter estimation technique is derived. This parameter estimation technique is then applied to the test cases implemented to determine the inputs of the 1D model that fit the pressure and flow rate results of the 3D numerical simulation.

The structure of the report is elucidated. In chapter 2 the background of the analytical model and past attempts to estimate arterial parameters are given. Then in chapter 3 the implementation of the analytical model is described, and the test cases of arterial networks are introduced. After that in chapter 4 the parameter estimation technique is derived and its application to each test case is elucidated. Thereafter the results are presented and discussed in chapter 5. Finally, the report is concluded in chapter 6.

Chapter 2

Background & Literature Review

This chapter presents the background of the analytical model and how it can be used to find the complex amplitudes of pressure and volume flow rate in the vessel. It also discusses past attempts to estimate arterial parameters using 1D models as well as alternative tools that are useful in arterial parameter estimation.

2.1 Analytical Model

In order to derive the analytical solution, inviscid, incompressible and axisymmetric flow and a zero steady velocity component is assumed in the Navier-Stokes and continuity equations which then simplify to the following in spherical coordinates (Papadakis, 2011):

$$\frac{1}{s^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial s} (s^2 u_s) + \frac{1}{s \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} (u_\theta \sin \theta) = 0 \quad \frac{\partial u_s}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial s} \quad (2.1)$$

In the equations above, u denotes velocity, ρ represents the density of blood and p denotes pressure. θ and s represent the axial and radial components of the spherical coordinate system. Figure 2.1 displays and defines the basic geometric parameters of the vessel by assuming a conical vessel in spherical coordinates. This includes the length coordinate used, s which can be derived from the horizontal length coordinate, x and taper angle of the vessel, α , using trigonometry: $s = (R_{in} - x \tan \alpha) / \sin \alpha$.

Figure 2.1: Diagram of a single vessel defined in spherical coordinates (Papadakis, 2011)

The simplified form of the Navier-Stokes and continuity equations allow for an analytical equation for pressure and volume flow rate in the frequency domain. The equation for pressure and flow rate amplitudes (ie. in the frequency domain) in a vessel based on the length coordinate, s and angular

frequency, ω is given by the following equations (Papadakis, 2011):

$$P(s, \omega) = s^{-1/2} (AJ_{1/3}(z) + BY_{1/3}(z)) \quad Q(s, \omega) = -iY(s)s^{-1/2} (AJ_{4/3}(z) + BY_{4/3}(z)) \quad (2.2)$$

Here, J and Y are Bessel functions of the first and second kind, respectively, and A and B are coefficients to be found using the boundary conditions at the two ends of the vessel, described in section 3.2. The real argument, z of the Bessel functions is given by the following formulae:

$$z = \frac{2}{3}\omega\sqrt{\rho\phi s^3} \quad \phi = \beta \frac{\tan^2 \alpha \sin \alpha}{1 - \cos \alpha} \quad \beta = \frac{1 - \nu^2}{Eh} \quad (2.3)$$

In this equation, ρ is the density of blood in the vessel and β is a consolidation of arterial wall mechanical properties including Poisson ratio, ν , Young's Modulus, E and wall thickness, h . Additionally, the admittance of the vessel can be computed using the mentioned quantities:

$$Y(s) = 2\pi(1 - \cos \alpha) \sqrt{\frac{\phi \cdot s^5}{\rho}} \quad (2.4)$$

Note that the definition of admittance; $Y(s)$, is distinct from that of Bessel functions of order $1/3$ or $4/3$; $Y_{1/3}(z)$ or $Y_{4/3}(z)$.

2.2 Parameter Estimation with State Space Models

Parameter estimation techniques are employed to determine inputs to the model, such as the one in section 2.1 using the model and the outputs thereof (ie. pressure and volume flow rate). These inputs to be determined include geometrical properties, such as the length and radius of the vessel, mechanical properties, such as stiffness and thickness of the vessel wall, as well as the Windkessel parameters (explained in section 3.2). Such estimation techniques have been studied in the context of arterial networks, and different techniques are employed depending on the number and type of measurements available and the inputs to be determined.

2.2.1 Subsystem Model Identification

One such estimation technique is described in (Kind et al., 2010) where Windkessel parameters are determined using a time domain model. The estimation procedure only used estimated values of pressure and attempted to maximise the goodness-of-fit of the estimated pressure curve to the true pressure curve. The goodness-of-fit was assessed using the variance-accounted-for (VAF) given by the following formula:

$$VAF(P(k), \hat{P}(k)) = 1 - \frac{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N |P(k) - \hat{P}(k)|^2}{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N |P(k)|^2} \quad (2.5)$$

This model was then fit using subspace model identification (SMI) and it was found that the Windkessel parameters could be determined using the pressure curve. That being said, this procedure was conducted in the time domain, whereas the analytical model described in section 2.1 is in the frequency domain.

2.2.2 Kalman Filter

Another method based on state space systems is using the Unscented Kalman Filter as described in (Caiazzo et al., 2017). The Unscented Kalman Filter is particularly useful as the models used are nonlinear, which makes the Kalman Filter inapplicable. The Kalman Filter is useful as it may estimate parameters that are both time invariant and time variant at the same time. This is particularly fruitful when only part of the measurements are available (such as either pressure or volume flow rate measurements only). That being said, state space methods are inconvenient to use with models in the frequency domain, as the inverse Fourier transform of the model outputs have to be computed at each iteration. Additionally, it is not particularly useful if the estimated parameters are time invariant. This is why it is useful to examine estimation procedures that are domain agnostic.

2.3 Parameter Estimation With Complex Models

While parameter estimation techniques in the time domain exist for relatively simple models, applying estimation techniques on arterial systems is relatively novel. This is because the conventional way to estimate parameters is by using a lumped parameter model, as done in (F. Huang & Ying, 2020).

2.3.1 Lumped (0D) Models

The principal difference between a 1D and 0D model is that in the 1D model, the pressure and flow rates spatially vary along the midpoint of the vessel (in contrast to 3D / CFD models in which they vary at each point in the vessel), whereas in 0D models the spatial average of pressure and flow rate is determined. The process of lumping involves formulating a complex arterial system as a rather simple model which returns the spatial average of pressure and flow rate, instead of the values at each point as in 3D models. The model used in (F. Huang & Ying, 2020) can be described by the diagram below:

Figure 2.2: 0D Lumped Parameter Model presented in (F. Huang & Ying, 2020)

The model is analogous to an electrical circuit model, with R denoting resistance, C , capacitance and L , inductance, while P and Q are pressure and volume flow rate, (analogous to voltage and current) respectively. This model is describable using a state space matrix system, which is then used to estimate parameters using nonlinear least squares regression (NLSR). NLSR is commonly used to fit a nonlinear model to a curve, which works by using an optimisation algorithm, most commonly stochastic gradient descent (H.-H. Huang, 2010). The algorithm attempts to minimise mean-squared-error (MSE):

$$MSE(\hat{\mathbf{x}}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (\hat{y}(t_n, \hat{\mathbf{x}}) - \tilde{y}(t_n))^2 \quad (2.6)$$

In this equation, t_n is the time step in question, \hat{y} is the estimated / modelled output (ie. pressure and flow rate) with $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ being the model inputs and \tilde{y} are the measurements. When mean-squared-error is minimised, the parameters that best fit the model to the measurements are found. The procedure used in chapter 4 is similar to the NLSR procedure, but with a more complicated cost function in a (possibly) different domain. While this procedure is described for a simple model, this can be generalised to more complex models.

2.3.2 Parameter Estimation in Arterial Systems

Determining parameters in large systems is a relatively challenging problem due (in part) to the large number of parameters involved. Moreover, the noninvasive measurements available could potentially be limited, which further complicates this problem. However, Itu et al. proposed a technique to estimate mechanical and Windkessel parameters in part of the aorta (Itu et al., 2018). This model involves three supra-aortic branches, each with a three Windkessel parameter outlet boundary condition, as shown in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3: Aortic Arch Model presented in (Itu et al., 2018)

In this paper, Itu et al. attempted to determine the linearly varying stiffness distribution for each of the seven segments in Figure 2.3. This means finding the stiffness at the inlet and outlet of every segment. Additionally, the Windkessel parameters at each of the four outlets was determined. The

measurements available included the cross sectional area and volume flow rate measurements at 50 points along the segments that were obtained from 4D MRI data. Additionally, the systolic and diastolic blood pressure measurements are also available at the left subclavian artery.

While the precise algorithm is confidential the methodology is described as follows. First an estimation of the average stiffness of the whole model is conducted using the systolic and diastolic pressure measurements with the help of a 1D model that returns pressure as an output. Thereafter, with this known, a NLSR is performed to determine the Windkessel parameters using the pressure and flow rate data, as well as the outputs of the 1D model for pressure. Finally, the estimate of the stiffness along each segment is refined using NLSR with the area measurements. This is done multiple times iteratively to refine the estimation of all parameters until the convergence criteria are met. This could be done as the used 1D model for pressure is in the time domain, and so the input parameters could be solved for analytically given the time varying values of pressure.

2.4 Alternative Models & Tools

Although there are studies done on arterial parameter estimation, there now exist software packages which are useful in creating and using 0D, 1D and 3D models. One such package is VaMpy, a Python module to solve 1D blood flows (Diem & Bressloff, 2017).

However, one particular computer programme of interest is SimVascular (Updegrave et al., 2017), which is an open source tool for simulating blood flows. In addition to being able to run 1D and 3D simulations on models of different blood vessels with ease, SimVascular also has the capability to develop models for arterial networks based on ultrasound images, which allows the geometrical parameters of the arteries to be noninvasively measured. As such, geometrical properties of many arterial systems such as the aorta do not need to be estimated using the parameter estimation procedure described in chapter 4.

Chapter 3

Methodology: Analytical Model

In this chapter the analytical model discussed in (Efstathiou & Papadakis, 2021) is generalised and the new implementation thereof is discussed. In principal the new implementation is also in an object oriented vectorised form, making it simpler to apply to more complex networks of arteries. The main aspect of the model that is expanded is the implementation for networks of single vessels, while the bifurcation model largely remains the same as in (Efstathiou & Papadakis, 2021).

3.1 Arterial Networks & Vessel Types

Depending on the location of the vessel within the arterial system, its boundary conditions are varied. There are potentially four types of vessels in an arterial system with each being handled differently. They are listed below while their diagrams are shown in Appendix A.

Type I. Inlet and outlet of the arterial system (Figure A.1)

Type II. Outlet but not inlet of the system, with another vessel connected at the inlet (Figure A.2)

Type III. Neither inlet nor outlet, a vessel connected to another on both ends (Figure A.3)

Type IV. Inlet but not outlet, with another vessel connected at the outlet (Figure A.4)

3.2 Backpropagation

The coefficients, A and B are partially determined using the outlet boundary condition, which may depend on other vessels depending on its type. Hence, the term 'backpropagation' as the properties of the current vessel depend on the properties of its successors, until the outlet(s) of the network.

If the vessel is the outlet of the system (ie. it is of type I or II) then the Windkessel Impedance model is used, as described in (Efstathiou & Papadakis, 2021). Here, the ratio between pressure and flow rate amplitudes is defined and termed as the impedance, Z :

$$Z = \frac{P_{out}}{Q_{out}} = \frac{R_1 + R_2 - i\omega R_1 R_2 C_{WK}}{1 - i\omega R_2 C_{WK}} \quad (3.1)$$

The impedance depends on three quantities, namely the first and second resistances; R_1 , R_2 and the capacitance; C_{WK} . Using this equation, and substituting the definitions of P_{out} and Q_{out} the ratio of

the coefficients, B/A can be determined in terms of Z :

$$\frac{B}{A} = -\frac{J_{1/3}(z_{out}) + iZY(s_{out})J_{4/3}(z_{out})}{Y_{1/3}(z_{out}) + iZY(s_{out})Y_{4/3}(z_{out})} \quad (3.2)$$

The subscripts 'in' and 'out' refer to quantities at the inlet and outlet of the vessel.

However, if the vessel is connected to another vessel at the outlet (ie. it is of type III or IV) then the effective admittance at the inlet of the successive vessel j , $Y_{eff}(s_{j,in})$ is used to determine B/A :

$$\frac{B}{A} = -\frac{iY(s_{out})J_{4/3}(s_{in}) + Y_{eff}(s_{j,in})J_{1/3}(s_{out})}{Y_{eff}(s_{j,in})Y_{1/3}(s_{out}) + iY(s_{out})Y_{4/3}(s_{out})} \quad (3.3)$$

The effective admittance at the inlet of the successive vessel can be computed using the properties of that vessel:

$$Y_{eff}(s_{j,in}) = -iY(s_{j,in}) \frac{J_{4/3}(z_{j,in}) + \frac{B_j}{A_j}Y_{4/3}(z_{j,in})}{J_{1/3}(z_{j,in}) + \frac{B_j}{A_j}Y_{1/3}(z_{j,in})} \quad (3.4)$$

In this equation, B_j/A_j may be determined using Equation 3.2 or Equation 3.3 for the successor in question, depending on its type.

3.3 Forward Propagation

Forward propagation utilises the properties (such as flow rate or pressure) computed for a vessels predecessor to determine properties for the vessel in question. If it is an inlet vessel for the whole network, (such as a type I or IV vessel), then the complex amplitude of the flow rate at the inlet, Q_{BC} must be given to determine A and therefore B :

$$A = -\frac{Q_{BC}}{iY(s)s^{-1/2}(J_{4/3}(z) + (B/A)Y_{4/3}(z))} \quad (3.5)$$

However, if the vessel is connected, (such as a type II or III vessel) then the pressure at the outlet at the previous vessel, P_{in} , is used as an inlet boundary condition to determine A :

$$A = \frac{P_{in}}{s_{in}^{-0.5}(J_{1/3}(s_{in}) + (B/A)Y_{1/3}(s_{in}))} \quad (3.6)$$

Finally, with A determined, B may can be computed with the ratio of the coefficients: $B = (B/A) \cdot A$ which then means the pressure and flow rate amplitudes may be computed in the frequency domain.

3.4 Bifurcation Model

A bifurcation is the splitting of a parent vessel into two daughter vessels. The model is presented in (Efstathiou & Papadakis, 2021). In principal there are six types of bifurcations, analogous to the four types of single vessels:

Type I. Parent vessel being an inlet and daughter vessels being outlets of the whole arterial system.

Type II. Parent vessel being connected to another vessel but daughter vessels being outlets of the system.

Type III. Only one daughter being an outlet to the system but both parent and other daughter being connected to other vessels.

Type IV. The parent vessel being an inlet and one daughter being an outlet to the system while the other daughter is connected to another vessel.

Type V. The parent being an inlet while both daughters are connected to other vessels in the system.

Type VI. All vessels (parent and both daughters) being connected to other vessels.

3.5 Inlet Boundary Condition & Fourier Transform

In order to use the volume flow rate at the inlet of the arterial system as a boundary condition for the model, it needs to be converted to the frequency domain. For this, the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) is used. Finally, when the results in the frequency domain are computed by model, they are then converted to the time domain using the inverse DFT. The definitions of both are given as follows where A_0 denotes the time-averaged value of the quantity:

$$X_k = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x_n \cdot e^{-\frac{i2\pi}{N}kn} \quad x_n = \frac{A_0}{2} + Re \left[\sum_{k=1}^K 2X_k e^{i\omega_k t} \right] \quad (3.7)$$

3.6 Test Cases Used to Validate the Model

There are five test cases considered, and each of these have a set of 3D numerical simulation results and known input parameter values. That is why these are very useful in validating the parameter estimation technique discussed. All test cases (including diagrams and parameter values) are obtained from chapter 5 of (Efsthathiou & Papadakis, 2021). These include the following, the diagrams of which are included in Appendix A:

Test Case I. Upper thoracic aorta (Figure A.5)

Test Case II. Common carotid artery (Figure A.6)

Test Case III. Tapered aorta (Figure A.7)

Test Case IV. Single Bifurcation model (Figure A.8)

Test Case V. Full aorta model (Figure A.9)

In the full aorta model, there are three types of bifurcations present. Bifurcation 10-19-20 is a type II bifurcation, whereas bifurcation 1-11-2 is a type IV bifurcation. The rest are type III bifurcations as they have one daughter that is an outlet and the other two are connected to other vessels.

Chapter 4

Methodology: Parameter Estimation

In this chapter the parameter estimation technique is derived and discussed. Furthermore, its application to the five test cases mentioned in section 3.6 is elucidated.

4.1 Derivation of Cost Function

In order to fit a model with a set of (supposedly unknown) parameters; \mathbf{x} , with outputs; \mathbf{y} , an optimisation problem is constructed whereby the cost function thereof is derived in the manner described herein. Three essential quantities include the time variant parameters (typically involving pressure and volume flow rate):

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \omega) = \text{Estimated (ie. modelled) outputs}$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{y}}(\omega) = \text{3D Numerical Solution Results}$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{y}}(\omega) = \hat{\mathbf{y}}(\bar{\mathbf{x}}, \omega) = \text{Estimated (modelled) outputs of known parameters, } \bar{\mathbf{x}}$$

The third parameter refers to the a priori values of the model, for the test cases computed in (Efstathiou & Papadakis, 2021). In principal, this procedure may be applied equivalently in the frequency, as well as the time domain. The domain is inconsequential to the optimisation procedure if consistently implemented due to the uniqueness of the Fourier Transformation.

The Mean-Squared-Relative-Error (MSRE) is determined using Equation 4.1 for scalar values of measurements and estimated model outputs, wherein N_ω denotes the number of time steps computed by the model for the output in question:

$$MSRE(\tilde{\mathbf{y}}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}) = \frac{1}{N_\omega} \sum_{j=1}^{N_\omega} \left| \frac{\tilde{y}(\omega_j) - \hat{y}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \omega_j)}{\tilde{y}(\omega_j)} \right|^2 \quad (4.1)$$

The cost function used in the algorithm, $\tilde{f}(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$, can then be defined as the sum of the MSRE of all the components in the model output vector; $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$, with respect to the measurements; $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}$:

$$\tilde{f}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}) = \sum_{i=1}^{dim(\hat{\mathbf{y}})} MSRE(\tilde{y}_i, \hat{y}_i) = \sum_{i=1}^{dim(\hat{\mathbf{y}})} \left[\frac{1}{N_\omega} \sum_{j=1}^{N_\omega} \left| \frac{\tilde{y}_i(\omega_j) - \hat{y}_i(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \omega_j)}{\tilde{y}_i(\omega_j)} \right|^2 \right] \quad (4.2)$$

In this equation, $dim(\hat{\mathbf{y}})$ denotes the number of components in the output vector, and the tilde on

the function represents that this is the cost function with respect to the measurements. The cost function with respect to the analytical solution; $\bar{f}(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$, is analogously defined by substituting \bar{y}_i instead of \tilde{y}_i . Note that $\bar{f}(\bar{\mathbf{x}}) = 0$. By minimising the cost function by means of an optimisation algorithm as described in section 4.2, the MSRE of all the parameters relative to their measured quantity is minimised. The MSRE is chosen in contrast to other forms of error (eg. Mean-Absolute-Error) due to its nondimensional form which does not unfairly penalise the quantities that may have higher errors due to the magnitudes of their respective dimensions. They are later summed as each output is assumed to hold equal importance and measurement error.

4.2 Optimisation Procedure

In order to minimise the cost function derived in section 4.1, an optimisation algorithm is used. For this purpose, several optimisation algorithms are explored and implemented and several techniques to improve convergence are utilised.

4.2.1 Optimisation Algorithms

Given is a description of the main algorithms used to minimise the cost function for each test case.

Nelder-Mead Simplex Method

The algorithm uses a set of test points (beginning with just the initial guess) and then searches for new better points through geometrical manipulations of the vertices including: reflection, expansion, contraction and shrinking and updating the set of test points when better values are found. It is generally used to determine the exact values of the parameters when the cost function with respect to the model outputs using known parameters, $\bar{f}(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$ is minimised.

Additionally, in order to find an estimate with a significantly greater precision when using the Nelder-Mead Simplex method, the estimate of one epoch of approximately 700 iterations is fed as input to another epoch. Thus effectively continuing the optimisation with re-initialised parameters between epochs. This technique is also known as boosting, and results in estimates orders of magnitude better than one epoch of equal iterations. This is likely attributable to the vertices in the algorithm being reset each time the algorithm is restarted thereby reducing its susceptibility of becoming stuck in the same pattern as before. (Ludl, 2012)

Its advantages include the fact that it uses the geometry of the cost function, (Ludl, 2012) which is advantageous due to the cost function in question being quite convex in the region of the solution. Furthermore, it also does not require computation of the gradient of the function as it is a search algorithm. (Ludl, 2012)

That being said, it may not work very well with a large input size when the initial estimate is far from the minimum due to its worse case convergence time scaling exponentially with the size of the input variable. (Ludl, 2012)

Interior-Point method

A constrained optimisation problem is converted to an unconstrained optimisation problem with a transformation of cost function to a barrier function. This barrier function is minimised by applying

Newton's method with the gradient of the barrier function. This is generally used when performing the optimisation relative to the 3D numerical simulation data, $\tilde{f}(\hat{x})$ as the global minimum may result in nonphysical values for the estimates.

It is used because the interior point method is able to solve constrained optimisation problems, and it has polynomial time complexity and works well for sparse problems with many dimensions. (Illés & Terlaky, 2002)

However, it does come with shortcomings, which include the fact that it is highly complex to implement. That being said, a Matlab's `fmincon` function is used, which has this implemented. Furthermore, this algorithm requires a computation of the gradient of the barrier function, which is a transformed form of the cost function. (Illés & Terlaky, 2002)

This algorithm is unlike the Nelder-Mead Simplex algorithm, and they each have complementary use cases and advantages, which is why both are used as necessary.

4.2.2 Parameter Preprocessing

To improve the convergence and optimisation aspects of the model and prevent convergence to non-ideal inflection points, the parameters to be estimated is preprocessed prior to their use with an optimisation algorithm. The inputs are normalised to the range 0 and 1 with a non-singular transformation S , with $\mathbf{0}$ being the zero vector with the same number of dimensions as \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{x}' :

$$S : \mathbf{x}' \mapsto \mathbf{x} \in [\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{0} + 1], \quad \forall \mathbf{x}' \in [\mathbf{x}'_{min}, \mathbf{x}'_{max}] \quad (4.3)$$

This is done so the algorithm needs to converge to values between 0 and 1 while the model itself may use the inversely scaled values once substituted into the cost function. The minimum and maximum value of each parameter is selected based on the literature values of the parameters (Flores, Alastruey & Poiré, 2016). That being said, the values themselves are of little concern as they are not necessarily constraining. The simplest non-singular transformation is the following element-wise linear transformation, otherwise known as Min/Max Scaling (Brownlee, 2020):

$$x = S(x') = \frac{x' - x'_{min}}{x'_{max} - x'_{min}} \quad x' = S^{-1}(x) = (x'_{max} - x'_{min})x + x'_{min} \quad (4.4)$$

Additionally, before performing the recursive optimisation, a suitable initial estimate is required. The estimate is selected in a strategic but unbiased manner. That is accomplished by sampling the guess; $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0$ from the standard uniform distribution, assuming $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 \sim U(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{0} + 1)$. A tuned parameter, f_{con} constrains the initial function value ($f(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0) \leq f_{con}$) to specify if an initial guess is deemed suitable. This method is appropriate as it does not incorporate bias for the initial guess, considering the a priori values are known.

4.2.3 Parameter Postprocessing

Once the optimal parameters are determined, the inverse transform of the Min/Max scaling operation is used to convert them to their original scales. Then, the Relative Deviation (RelDif) between them and the known values are computed using the following element-wise equation:

$$RelDif(\bar{x}, \hat{x}) = \left| \frac{\bar{x} - \hat{x}}{\bar{x}} \right| \quad (4.5)$$

4.3 Windkessel Parameter Estimation

The Windkessel parameters may be determined independently from the rest of the model input parameters. This is because the Windkessel parameters are directly related to the pressure and volume flow rate at the corresponding outlet of the vessel, as formulated in Equation 3.1. As such, they may be determined using the described complex nonlinear least squares regression procedure.

In this case, the pressure and volume flow rate values from the 3D numerical simulation are transformed to the frequency domain, and the former is divided by the latter. This is then used to determine the values of the three Windkessel parameters, $\hat{x} = [R_1, R_2, C_{WK}]^T$ that minimise the following cost function:

$$\tilde{f}_Z(\hat{x}) = \frac{1}{N_\omega} \sum_{n=1}^{N_\omega} \left| \tilde{Z}(\omega_n) - \hat{Z}(\hat{x}, \omega_n) \right|^2 \quad \tilde{Z}(\omega) = \frac{\tilde{P}_{out}(\omega)}{\tilde{Q}_{out}(\omega)} \quad (4.6)$$

In this equation, $\hat{Z}(\hat{x}, \omega_n)$ is defined by the three Windkessel parameters in Equation 3.1 and \tilde{P}_{out} and \tilde{Q}_{out} are the Fourier transform of the 3D numerical simulation values of the pressure and volume flow rates at the outlet in question.

4.4 Estimated Parameters & Data Utilised

Depending on the test case, the input vector, x has different components. Additionally, each test case uses different information for pressure and flow rate at unique points along the vessel(s) in the network.

4.4.1 Single Vessel Models

For the case of single vessel models (ie. test cases I-III), the unknowns include β ; the consolidation of mechanical properties from Equation 2.3, L ; the length of the vessel, R_i ; the inlet radius of the vessel as well as the three Windkessel parameters: R_1, R_2, C_{WK} . The data used to estimate them include the pressure at the inlet, as well as the pressure and volume flow rate at the midpoint and outlet of the vessel. Note that the volume flow rate at the inlet is not used because it serves as a boundary condition for the model, as described in section 3.3. Therefore, the input and output vectors for the single vessel models may be expressed as the following:

$$x = [L, R_i, \beta, R_1, R_2, C_{WK}]^T \quad y = [P_i, P_m, Q_m, P_o, Q_o]^T \quad (4.7)$$

Here, the subscripts i, m and o denote the values at the inlet, midpoint and outlet, respectively.

4.4.2 Bifurcation Model

On the other hand, for the single bifurcation (test case IV), which is a connection of three vessels, the geometrical and mechanical properties must be determined for all three vessels and the Windkessel parameters must be determined for the outlets of the two daughters. This implies a total of 15 parameters to be optimised. However, a major simplification is made to reduce the number of optimised parameters to 9. The simplification involves treating both daughter vessels as identical, which means that they both have the same length, radius, mechanical properties and Windkessel parameters as each other. The location of the 3D simulated pressures and flow rates include the inlet of the parent vessel, midpoint of the parent vessel, junction, midpoint of a daughter vessel, and the outlet of a daughter vessel. The input and output vectors may thereby be expressed as the following, where the subscripts p and d signify attributes of the parent and daughter vessels:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x} &= [L_p, R_{i,p}, \beta_p, L_p, R_{i,d}, \beta_d, R_1, R_2, C_{WK}]^T \\ \mathbf{y} &= [P_{i,p}, P_{m,p}, Q_{m,p}, P_j, Q_j, P_{m,d}, Q_{m,d}, P_{o,d}, Q_{o,d}]^T \end{aligned} \quad (4.8)$$

In the above equation, the subscript j denotes values at the junction of the bifurcation.

4.4.3 Full Aorta Model

Finally, for the full aorta model (test case V), there are a total of 20 vessels each with their mechanical and geometrical properties. The parameter estimation technique forgoes the estimation of the geometrical properties to simplify the procedure. Additionally, geometrical properties can be measured noninvasively with the use of ultrasound imaging technology (Updegrave et al., 2017), which is why it is not as imperative to estimate using this method as the mechanical and Windkessel parameters.

This is in principal a 50 parameter optimisation problem as it consists of 20 values of β and 3 Windkessel parameters at 10 outlets. However, additional techniques are used to simplify this large optimisation problem. Firstly, the Windkessel parameters at outlets 17 and 20 are assumed to be identical to those at outlets 16 and 19, respectively, as the 3D simulation values are not known at these outlets. Secondly, the Windkessel parameters at all other outlets are first estimated using the technique involving the pressure and flow rate at those outlets elucidated in section 4.3. This is with the exception of the Windkessel parameters at outlet 14, which may not assumed to be identical to any other outlet, nor may it be estimated using the procedure described in section 4.3 due to the 3D simulated values not being given for this outlet. As such, it is estimated along with the values for β of all vessels. This means that as the Windkessel parameters of almost all the outlets are determined independently, the estimation technique described in section 4.1 is first applied to the following 23 parameters:

$$\mathbf{x} = [\beta, R_{1,14}, R_{2,14}, C_{WK,14}]^T \quad \beta = [\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_{20}] \quad (4.9)$$

The 3D simulation data available include the pressure and flow rate at the inlet, and outlets 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, 18 and 19. Therefore all the data except the volume flow rate at the inlet of the model are used for the estimation of the mechanical properties of all vessels and the Windkessel parameters at the outlet of vessel 14:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{y} &= [P_{i,1}, \mathbf{P}_o, \mathbf{Q}_o]^T \\
\mathbf{P}_o &= [P_{o,11}, P_{o,12}, P_{o,13}, P_{o,15}, P_{o,16}, P_{o,18}, P_{o,19}] \\
\mathbf{Q}_o &= [Q_{o,11}, Q_{o,12}, Q_{o,13}, Q_{o,15}, Q_{o,16}, Q_{o,18}, Q_{o,19}]
\end{aligned} \tag{4.10}$$

Once these parameters are estimated, the estimation is then refined in a large optimisation procedure involving all the unknown parameters. This is done since using nonlinear least squares regression on the impedance model results in an error in the Windkessel parameters at that outlet, which then results in additional errors for all the parameters.

While this is considered a worthwhile estimation of the parameters, this estimation is refined using all the measurements available and optimising all parameters together, with the assumption that the Windkessel parameters of 17 and 20 as well as those of 16 and 19 being equivalent to one another. Therefore, this $50 - 3 \times 2 = 44$ parameter optimisation requires a significant amount of computing time.

However, as the initial estimate is already provided from the previous optimisation procedure, this is only used to refine that estimate. As such, few iterations of this is necessary for this procedure to converge to a set of suitable values. It is also capable of determining the values of the parameters that best fit the output values in relatively fewer iterations due to the simplifying assumptions implemented in the technique. The input parameters determined (or refined, to be precise) in this procedure are mathematically formulated in the equation below:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{x} &= [\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_2, \mathbf{C}_{WK}]^T \\
\mathbf{R}_1 &= [R_{1,11}, R_{1,12}, R_{1,13}, R_{1,14}, R_{1,15}, R_{1,16}, R_{1,18}, R_{1,19}] \\
\mathbf{R}_2 &= [R_{2,11}, R_{2,12}, R_{2,13}, R_{2,14}, R_{2,15}, R_{2,16}, R_{2,18}, R_{2,19}] \\
\mathbf{C}_{WK} &= [C_{WK,11}, C_{WK,12}, C_{WK,13}, C_{WK,14}, C_{WK,15}, C_{WK,16}, C_{WK,18}, C_{WK,19}]
\end{aligned} \tag{4.11}$$

4.5 Estimation Evaluation Metrics

Once the parameters are estimated, some metrics are used to find how well the pressure and flow rate curves fit to the 3D results with the estimated parameters. These metrics are particularly useful to evaluate the quality of the fit as they are given in relative (or percentage) terms, instead of units of the quantities. The first metric is the average relative error (Efstathiou & Papadakis, 2021):

$$\epsilon_{y,avg} = \frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} \left| \frac{\hat{y}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, t_j) - \tilde{y}(t_j)}{\tilde{y}(t_j)} \right| \tag{4.12}$$

Another useful metric is the maximum relative error (Efstathiou & Papadakis, 2021):

$$\epsilon_{y,max} = \max_j \left| \frac{\hat{y}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, t_j) - \tilde{y}(t_j)}{\tilde{y}(t_j)} \right| \tag{4.13}$$

The relative error of the quantities in systole is also given (Efstathiou & Papadakis, 2021):

$$\epsilon_{y,sys} = \frac{\max_j(\hat{y}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, t_j)) - \max_j(\tilde{y}(t_j))}{\max_j(\tilde{y}(t_j))} \tag{4.14}$$

Finally, the relative error of the quantities in diastole is given in the following equation (Efstathiou & Papadakis, 2021):

$$\epsilon_{q,dias} = \frac{\min_j(\hat{q}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, t_j)) - \min_j(\tilde{q}(t_j))}{\max_j(\tilde{q}(t_j))} \quad \epsilon_{p,dias} = \frac{\min_j(\hat{p}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, t_j)) - \min_j(\tilde{p}(t_j))}{\min_j(\tilde{p}(t_j))} \quad (4.15)$$

For the first three, the type of quantity does not matter. However the diastolic relative error is computed differently for pressure and volume flow rate.

Chapter 5

Results & Discussion

This chapter aims to present and discuss the results obtained when attempting to estimate the parameters in each of the five test cases mentioned in section 3.6. While the estimation procedure is first verified on the model outputs with the known parameters, $\bar{\mathbf{y}}$, the results that are presented are the ones that fit the model to the 3D numerical simulation results, $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}$. This is because in all of the test cases the exact parameter values can be found when the estimation procedure is used to fit the curves to the model outputs that use the known parameters.

5.1 Upper Thoracic Aorta (UTA)

The UTA is one of three cases of single vessels, for which the length, radius, mechanical property (β) and Windkessel parameters are determined and presented in Table 5.1. To first determine whether the parameter estimation technique is valid for this case, the parameters are fit to the curves of the model outputs given the known values. This yields a cost function value of $\tilde{f}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}) = 7.92 \times 10^{-27}$.

Input Units	L m	R_{in} m	β m/N	R_1 $10^7 Pa \cdot s/m^3$	R_2 $10^8 Pa \cdot s/m^3$	C_{WK} $10^{-8} m^3/Pa$
Known Value	0.241	0.0127	0.0016	1.18	1.12	1.02
Optimised Value	0.231	0.0117	0.0018	1.17	1.11	1.01
RelDif (%)	4.15	7.53	12.3	0.676	0.756	0.223

Table 5.1: Results of the Upper Thoracic Aorta Case

The cost function is minimised to a value of $\tilde{f}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}) = 0.00087$, whereas the known values yield a cost function value of $\tilde{f}(\bar{\mathbf{x}}) = 0.0024$. This indicates that the fit of the optimised values is significantly better than that of the known values. In order to visualise this fit, Figures 5.1 to 5.3 are inspected, in contrast to those found in section B.1 in Appendix B.

The pressure at the inlet, as shown in Figure 5.1a is shown to fit comparatively better than with the known values, as shown in Figure B.1. This is indicated by the fact that the average relative deviation from the 3D simulation values is lower in the case of the optimised parameters, although the maximum deviation is slightly greater.

In Figure 5.2a the pressure is seen to be fit well with the optimised parameters, as well as the flow rate in Figure 5.2b. This is evident as all the deviations are comparatively lower for the pressure when

Figure 5.1: Flow Properties at the Inlet of the UTA

Figure 5.2: Flow Properties at the Midpoint of the UTA

the estimated parameters are used in contrast to known ones in Figure B.2, and all except maximum deviation is lower for volume flow rate.

Figure 5.3a shows that the pressure derived from the estimated parameters agrees with the numerical simulation more than that of the a priori parameters in Figure B.3. However, the optimised volume flow rate in Figure 5.3b has a larger maximum deviation compared to that in Figure B.3b but is otherwise a better fit.

5.2 Common Carotid Artery

The estimated parameters for the case of the common carotid artery can be found in Table 5.2. The parameters are found by minimising the cost function to a value of $\tilde{f}(\hat{\boldsymbol{x}}) = 0.0002153$, whereas the known values yields a cost function value of $\tilde{f}(\bar{\boldsymbol{x}}) = 0.0002742$.

It is thereby evident that according to the specified cost function, the optimised parameters fits the results of the 3D simulation better than the known parameters. However, this causes a deviation in the parameter values. The maximum deviation is found to be a 10.7% deviation in the length of the artery. Additionally, to verify the test case, the cost function relative to the outputs of the model using the known values is minimised to a value of $\tilde{f}(\hat{\boldsymbol{x}}) = 1.67 \times 10^{-28}$. In doing so, the parameters could

Figure 5.3: Flow Properties at the Outlet of the UTA

Input	L	R_{in}	β	R_1	R_2	C_{WK}
Units	m	m	m/N	$10^8 Pa \cdot s/m^3$	$10^9 Pa \cdot s/m^3$	$10^{-10} m^3/Pa$
Known Value	0.126	0.0030	0.0036	2.49	1.87	1.75
Optimised Value	0.139	0.0030	0.0034	2.73	1.85	1.75
RelDif (%)	10.7	0.354	4.27	9.78	0.930	0.271

Table 5.2: Results of the Common Carotid Artery Case

be determined exactly, with the maximum relative deviation being $2.4 \times 10^{-11}\%$ in the value of β .

In the optimisation process, the algorithm typically converges to similar values, although (due to the randomness of the estimation procedure) the algorithm sometimes does not converge, or converges to completely different parameters. However, in both cases the cost function values computed are particularly large which indicates that the values (possibly) found are not an optimal fit.

5.3 Tapered Aorta

The tapered aorta is much like the common carotid artery and upper thoracic aorta except for the fact that it has a relatively large taper angle. As such the input parameters to be determined remain the same.

Input	L	R_{in}	β	R_1	R_2	C_{WK}
Units	m	m	m/N	$10^7 Pa \cdot s/m^3$	$10^8 Pa \cdot s/m^3$	$10^{-8} m^3/Pa$
Known Value	0.241	0.015	0.0016	1.85	1.05	1.02
Optimised Value	0.208	0.013	0.0023	1.97	1.04	1.03
RelDif (%)	14	12	45	6.9	1.3	1.6

Table 5.3: Results of the Tapered Aorta Case

Table 5.3 displays the optimised parameters. The maximum deviation is that in β which deviates by 45% compared to the reference value. To determine these parameters the cost function is minimised to a value of $\tilde{f}(\hat{x}) = 0.00085$ which is significantly lower than the cost function value of the known parameters, $\tilde{f}(\bar{x}) = 0.0014$.

5.4 Single Bifurcation

The single bifurcation case is unlike the the single vessel in the sense that it has one parent vessel that channels blood into two daughters, both of which have Windkessel models at the outlet, as shown in Figure A.8.

Input Units	L_p m	$R_{in,p}$ m	β_p m/N	L_d m	$R_{in,d}$ m	β_d m/N
Known Value	0.086	0.0089	0.001453	0.085	0.006125	0.001488
Optimised Value	0.106	0.0090	0.001074	0.1335	0.0059	0.001047
RelDif (%)	23	0.63	26	57	3.2	30

Table 5.4: Geometrical & Mechanical Properties of the Single Bifurcation Case

Table 5.4 displays the length, radius and mechanical consolidation factor of the parent and both (identical) daughters in the single bifurcation case. The Windkessel parameters of both daughters are presented in Table 5.5. These values are found by minimising the cost function between the model and simulation results to a value of $\tilde{f}(\hat{x}) = 0.0030$. Compared to the known values which result in a cost function value of $\tilde{f}(\bar{x}) = 0.0041$ they seem to fit the 3D results significantly better.

Input Units	R_1 $10^7 Pa \cdot s/m^3$	R_2 $10^9 Pa \cdot s/m^3$	C_{WK} $10^{-10} m^3/Pa$
Known Value	6.8123	3.1013	3.6664
Optimised Value	8.62	3.08	3.54
RelDif (%)	27	0.75	3.4

Table 5.5: Windkessel Parameters of the Daughter Vessels in the Single Bifurcation Case

It can be seen that the maximum relative deviation between the two is that of the length of the daughter vessels, for which the optimised result is 57% greater than the known value. The minimum deviation is that of the inlet radius of the parent vessel, for which the optimised result is 0.63% greater than the known value. The results are also verified similarly to the previous cases whereby the cost function with respect to the 1D model solutions with the a priori inputs is optimised. Once again the exact parameter values could be found with a cost function value of $\tilde{f}(\hat{x}) = 7.1 \times 10^{-27}$ resulting in parameters with a maximum relative deviation of $4.85 \times 10^{-10}\%$. Figures 5.4 to 5.8 present the model outputs with the optimised results, with the outputs of the known results being included in section B.2. The purpose of these figures is to examine how well the estimated parameters fit the model to the 3D curves, in comparison to the known values thereof.

The inlet pressure displayed in Figure 5.4a fits relatively worse in comparison to the known values as shown in Figure B.4. This is most likely due to the estimation procedure sacrificing the fit of this value in favour of others which fit significantly better in a manner that compensates for the inlet pressure not fitting as well.

Figure 5.5a displays the pressure curve at the midpoint of the parent vessel, which is observed to fit worse than the known values as shown in Figure B.5. Once again, this is likely due to other values being fit more precisely. It can be seen in Figure 5.5b that the flow rate is fit comparatively better to the simulation results compared to Figure B.5b in all aspects.

The pressure in the junction for the optimised parameters (Figure 5.6a) is also fit worse than that with the known values (Figure B.6a). However, the volume flow rate is fit much better as can be seen in

Figure 5.4: Flow Properties at the Inlet of the Bifurcation

Figure 5.5: Flow Properties at the Midpoint of the Parent Vessel in the Bifurcation

Figures 5.6b and B.6b.

At the midpoint of the daughter vessel, the pressure is also fit worse with the optimised (Figure 5.7a) in comparison to the known parameters in Figure B.7a. The volume flow rate is in contrast fit better to the curved with the optimised values in Figure 5.7b when compared to the known values in Figure B.7b.

For the outlet, the pressure curve is fit slightly better with the estimated parameters in Figure 5.8a in comparison to the known parameters in Figure B.8a. This is indicated with a lower average percent error of 1.88% in contrast to 1.98%. However, the maximum error is still larger for the optimised results (3.90%) compared to the known values (3.48%). When looking at the volume flow rate, the optimised results in Figure 5.8b is fit significantly better to the 3D simulated curve when compared to the same curve with the previously known values in Figure 5.7b.

On the whole, it appears that the pressure curves are generally fit worse than the curves of the volume flow rate for the case of the bifurcation. There is no methodological reason for why this may be the case. However, it could be that the shape of the cost function happens to have a higher curvature in the direction which optimises the flow rate in comparison to the pressure.

Figure 5.6: Flow Properties at the Junction of the Bifurcation

Figure 5.7: Flow Properties at the Midpoint of the Daughter Vessel in the Bifurcation

5.5 Full Aorta

The full aorta is a large network of arteries, and as such requires many inputs. Furthermore, all the inputs are coupled to one another, so they cannot be optimised in smaller batches. That being said, with the estimation procedure described in subsection 4.4.3 the parameters may be determined. Tables 5.6 to 5.9 display the values of β for each vessel with the numbering style from Figure A.9.

β (m/N)	1	2	3	4	5
Known Value	0.00133	0.00140	0.00141	0.00139	0.00139
Optimised Value	0.00233	0.00140	0.00143	0.00110	0.00129
RelDif (%)	76	0.28	1.5	21	7.3

Table 5.6: Aortic Mechanical Properties of Vessels 1 to 5

The values of β are generally in agreement with the known values. However, the maximum relative deviation is 76% in β_1 , making it significantly greater than the known value. The minimum relative deviation is 0.28% in β_2 .

On the other hand for the first Windkessel resistances shown in Table 5.10, there is quite a large difference between the 3D simulated values and the known ones, especially for outlet 14 which has a 120% deviation between the known and optimised value. This is justifiable as outlet 14 is the

Figure 5.8: Flow Properties at the Outlet of the Daughter Vessel in the Bifurcation

β (m/N)	6	7	8	9	10
Known Value	0.00161	0.00162	0.00163	0.00161	0.00165
Optimised Value	0.00133	0.00152	0.00158	0.00113	0.00164
RelDif (%)	17	6.4	3.1	30	0.41

Table 5.7: Aortic Mechanical Properties of Vessels 6 to 10

only outlet for which the pressure and volume flow rate are unknown and dissimilar to any other outlet. Furthermore, this deviation affects the deviation of all other parameters as this system is highly coupled. As such, pressure and flow rate measurements at each outlet in an arterial system is of great significance to the precision of all the estimated parameters.

A similar trend may be observed in the case of the second Windkessel resistances displayed in Table 5.11. The fourteenth outlet results in the greatest discrepancy between the known and optimised parameters with a relative deviation of 34%. While this is considerably lower than that of the first Windkessel resistance at the same outlet, it is still the highest discrepancy. Once again this is attributable to the lack of measurements at the outlet to fit to, causing uncertainty in the value.

The Windkessel capacitance of each outlet vessel in the full aorta is presented in Table 5.12. Unlike the resistances, the capacitances are in good agreement with the known parameters, with the maximum relative deviation being 14% in vessel 15. This indicates that the parameter estimation technique is more effective for the capacitance than the two resistances. However, this is still uncertain.

The parameters are estimated by optimising the cost function of the full aorta model with respect to the 3D simulated results in a number of steps. The final value of the cost function is $\tilde{f}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}) = 0.00457$ which is more than four times lower than the cost function of the known parameters, that is, $\tilde{f}(\bar{\mathbf{x}}) = 0.0198$. This implies that, according to the cost function, the optimised parameters are a significantly better fit than the known ones. Furthermore, the procedure is verified by attempting to determine the exact parameters while minimising the cost function relative to the model solution using the known parameters. This yields a cost function value of $\bar{f}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}) = 9.83 \times 10^{-26}$, with the maximum relative deviation being $1.7 \times 10^{-9}\%$.

The pressure at the inlet of the first vessel is displayed in Figure 5.9a, which may be compared to Figure B.9. It can be observed that the optimised parameters fit to the simulation results slightly worse than the known parameters. This is since this measurement has been sacrificed for the fit of other measurements, as seen below.

$\beta (m/N)$	11	12	13	14	15
Known Value	0.00193	0.00242	0.00216	0.00222	0.00238
Optimised Value	0.00224	0.00255	0.00273	0.00241	0.00192
RelDif (%)	16	5.3	27	8.5	19

Table 5.8: Aortic Mechanical Properties of Vessels 11 to 15

$\beta (m/N)$	16	17	18	19	20
Known Value	0.00267	0.00267	0.00306	0.00197	0.00197
Optimised Value	0.00272	0.00291	0.00253	0.00148	0.00326
RelDif (%)	1.8	8.8	18	25	65

Table 5.9: Aortic Mechanical Properties of Vessels 16 to 20

Figure 5.10a shows the pressure at the outlet of vessel 11, which may be contrasted with that shown in Figure B.10a. Much like the pressure at the inlet, the pressure is fit slightly worse than with the known parameters. However, this is not the case for the volume flow rate at the same point which is shown in Figure 5.10b, and the same for the known values is shown in Figure B.10b. For this, the fit is significantly better for the optimised values in contrast to the previously known ones.

For outlet 12, the pressure curve for the optimised parameters may be seen in Figure 5.11a. The pressure at this outlet also seems to fit worse than when the known values are used, as shown in Figure B.11a. On the other hand, the volume flow rate at this outlet (Figure 5.11b) is observed to fit significantly better than with the known parameters in Figure B.11b.

At the outlet of vessel 13, the pressure determined from the optimised parameters (Figure 5.12a) is fit similarly to the known values seen in Figure B.12a. That being said, the volume flow rate in Figure 5.12b is fit significantly better than the one using the known values in Figure B.12b.

Figure 5.13a displays the pressure curve using the optimised parameters at the outlet of vessel 15. Unlike the previous pressure curves, the pressure at this point is fit to the 3D results significantly better than the curve using the known parameters shown in Figure B.13a. The volume flow rate at this outlet is also fit considerably better to the 3D results with the optimised parameters presented in Figure 5.13b, when compared to the one using the known parameter values in Figure B.13b.

At vessel 16, much like vessel 15, the pressure fits to the 3D results better with the optimised values (Figure 5.14a) compared to the known values (Figure B.14a). The same can be said about the flow rate at this point, since in Figure 5.14b the flow rate using the optimised values fits to the 3D curve very well compared to the one that uses the known values in Figure B.14b.

Figure 5.15a shows the pressure at the outlet of vessel 18, which may be contrasted with that shown in Figure B.15a. Much like the pressure at vessels 15 and 16, the pressure is fit better with the optimised values than with the known parameters. This is also the case for the volume flow rate at the same point which is shown in Figure 5.15b, and the flow rate for the known values is shown in Figure B.15b.

For the results at vessel 19 in Figure 5.16a, the pressure is fit better with the optimised values than the known results, which are shown in Figure B.16a. The same can be stated for the volume flow rate, which is shown in Figure 5.16b for the optimised values and Figure B.16b for the known values.

$R_1 (10^8 Pa \cdot s/m^3)$	11	12	13	14	15	16	18	19
Known Value	5.192	1.915	9.882	1.176	1.744	3.414	7.402	5.915
Optimised Value	4.324	1.562	8.737	2.588	1.965	3.729	8.059	5.517
RelDif (%)	17	18	12	120	13	9.2	8.9	6.7

Table 5.10: First Windkessel Resistance of Outlet Vessels in the Full Aorta

$R_2 (10^9 Pa \cdot s/m^3)$	11	12	13	14	15	16	18	19
Known Value	1.061	5.221	1.302	7.573	5.510	5.395	4.623	1.017
Optimised Value	1.065	5.332	1.296	5.018	5.428	5.351	4.584	1.037
RelDif (%)	0.40	2.1	0.46	34	1.5	0.81	0.83	1.9

Table 5.11: Second Windkessel Resistance of Outlet Vessels in the Full Aorta

5.6 Discussion

In this section, the results are discussed altogether to explain the various observations while running the parameter estimation procedure. On the whole, the modelled results are in good agreement with the 3D numerical simulation results for the optimised parameters, making it a successful estimation procedure.

Firstly, it appears as though the flow rates fit better than the pressure. That is due to the fact that the Windkessel model is used to determine pressure from volume flow rate, and so the deviations in Windkessel parameters affect pressure while not volume flow rate. This is shown in the case of the common carotid artery, wherein a pair of pressure and flow rate could be used to determine all parameters. However, one pressure measurement could not determine any parameters and one flow rate measurement could determine all except for the three Windkessel parameters. Furthermore, it is also observed that the fewer measurements used resulted in a lower precision in the estimated parameters, which is expected.

Additionally, in the bifurcation case the daughters are identical, and this is assumed in the estimation procedure as well. However, if this is not the case, a different method should be used. One possibility is using the Windkessel parameter estimation procedure outlined in section 4.3 for both daughters (if measurements at both outlets are available) and then optimise the rest together (L , R_{in} and β for the parent and two daughters).

It can also be seen that in the full aorta, there are many parameters to be determined, making the estimation of the geometrical parameters of each vessel impractical alongside the rest. However, if ultrasound images of the test case are available, then the geometrical parameters can be determined using a tool such as SimVascular (Updegrave et al., 2017).

For all graphs, the 3D simulation results were obtained from (Flores, Alastruey & Poiré, 2016) using a web plot digitizer (Rohatgi, 2021). Due to this, there are additional errors induced in the red curves above that are not due to any physical reason, which adversely affects the estimated value of the parameters.

The computer used to run the simulations has standard specifications, with an Intel i5 processor and 4GB RAM. The vectorisation in the implementation of the model is found to be beneficial as it runs the full aorta model in 76.8 milliseconds compared to the previous implementation which could run it in 143 milliseconds. The optimisation algorithm is relatively fast, as well as evaluations of the model.

C_{WK} ($10^{-10}m^3/Pa$)	11	12	13	14	15	16	18	19
Known Value	8.697	1.767	7.087	12.18	16.75	17.10	1.996	9.069
Optimised Value	9.069	1.888	7.388	12.31	19.11	17.77	2.184	9.661
RelDif (%)	4.3	6.8	4.2	1.0	14	3.9	9.4	6.5

Table 5.12: Capacitance of Outlet Vessels in the Full Aorta

Figure 5.9: Flow Properties at the Inlet of the Full Aorta

This makes the estimation procedure on the most complex case (the full aorta) take 5-10 minutes to run. This varies somewhat widely due to the randomness involved. That being said, the estimation technique for most test cases converged in a matter of seconds.

In the future, additional work can be done to attempt to determine the parameters of a real life test case, with noninvasive ultrasound images and/or blood pressure measurements. This can be done using a pipeline tool such as SimVascular to first create the model and estimate the geometrical properties of each vessel. This then may be utilised in the parameter estimation technique to determine the mechanical properties of each vessel, as shown in this report.

Figure 5.10: Flow Properties at the Outlet of Vessel 11

Figure 5.11: Flow Properties at the Outlet of Vessel 12

Figure 5.12: Flow Properties at the Outlet of Vessel 13

Figure 5.13: Flow Properties at the Outlet of Vessel 15

Figure 5.14: Flow Properties at the Outlet of Vessel 16

Figure 5.15: Flow Properties at the Outlet of Vessel 18

Figure 5.16: Flow Properties at the Outlet of Vessel 19

Chapter 6

Conclusion

The purpose of the report is to use a 1D analytical model in the frequency domain and the results of a 3D numerical simulation using known input parameters to estimate the same parameters for a few test cases of arterial networks.

In order to achieve this, a parameter estimation procedure is performed on a set of five test cases. The estimation procedure is able to determine the exact values of the parameters when it attempts to fit the curves to the analytical solutions with the known values. However, with the 3D numerical simulation results, it is able to determine the values for all test cases with a relative deviation of typically less than 20%, though this can be much higher for some (especially when there is a dearth of available measurements).

It can be argued that the model fits the measurements well as the cost function value tends to be significantly lower with the optimised results compared to the known values of the parameters. This is further exemplified by the fact that the curves of the pressure and volume flow rate appear to fit to the 3D numerical simulation results particularly well. However, they are unable to fit perfectly due to a number of reasons including a disparity in assumptions between the two models (3D versus 1D simulation) as well as the fact that the data is gathered using a web plot digitizer tool which introduces additional errors to the 3D numerical simulation data.

In order to improve this estimation procedure so that the geometrical parameters for the full aorta may be determined, additional methods are necessary. These can be found in tools such as SimVascular that are capable of modelling arterial networks with the help of in vivo measurements and ultrasound images. However, since the estimation procedure is able to determine arterial parameters for relatively large networks of arteries the objective of this project is achieved.

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Appendix A

Model & Test Case Diagrams

A.1 Single Vessel Types

Figure A.1: Diagram of Type I Vessel

Figure A.2: Diagram of Type II Vessel

Figure A.3: Diagram of Type III Vessel

Figure A.4: Diagram of Type IV Vessel

A.2 Test Cases

Figure A.5: Diagram of the Upper Thoracic Aorta (Xiao, Alastruey & Figueroa, 2014)

Figure A.6: Diagram of the Common Carotid Artery (Xiao, Alastruey & Figueroa, 2014)

Figure A.7: Diagram of the Tapered Aorta (Xiao, Alastruey & Figueroa, 2014)

Figure A.8: Diagram of the Single Bifurcation (Efstathiou & Papadakis, 2021)

Figure A.9: Diagram of the Full Aorta (Flores, Alastruey & Poiré, 2016)

Appendix B

Reference Results

This appendix contains images of results from the simulation run with the known input values, as seen in (Efstathiou & Papadakis, 2021). These are the values presented in (Flores, Alastruey & Poiré, 2016) for the full aorta case and (Xiao, Alastruey & Figueroa, 2014) for the rest.

B.1 Upper Thoracic Aorta (UTA)

Figure B.1: Previously Determined Pressure at the Inlet of the UTA

Figure B.2: Previously Determined Flow Properties at the Midpoint of the UTA

Figure B.3: Previously Determined Flow Properties at the Outlet of the UTA

B.2 Single Bifurcation

Figure B.4: Previously Determined Pressure at the Inlet of the Bifurcation

Figure B.5: Previously Determined Flow Properties at the Midpoint of the Parent Vessel in the Bifurcation

Figure B.6: Previously Determined Flow Properties at the Junction of the Bifurcation

Figure B.7: Previously Determined Flow Properties at the Midpoint of the Daughter Vessel in the Bifurcation

Figure B.8: Previously Determined Flow Properties at the Outlet of the Daughter Vessel in the Bifurcation

B.3 Full Aorta

Figure B.9: Previously Determined Pressure at the Inlet of the Full Aorta

Figure B.10: Previously Determined Flow Properties at the Outlet of Vessel 11

Figure B.11: Previously Determined Flow Properties at the Outlet of Vessel 12

Figure B.12: Previously Determined Flow Properties at the Outlet of Vessel 13

Figure B.13: Previously Determined Flow Properties at the Outlet of Vessel 15

Figure B.14: Previously Determined Flow Properties at the Outlet of Vessel 16

Figure B.15: Previously Determined Flow Properties at the Outlet of Vessel 18

Figure B.16: Previously Determined Flow Properties at the Outlet of Vessel 19